

OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG BANK EMPLOYEES

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Abstract:

In the cut throat competitive era job satisfaction and job stress are the two most widely studied topics in the present world. A major part of man's life is spent in work and hence stress level is increasing among the employees. Banking industry which is the backbone of the country's economy is not an exceptional one. During the past decade, the Indian banking sector has undergone rapid and striking changes due to globalization and liberalization, increased competition due to the entrance of more private sector banks, introduction of new technologies, etc. Due to these changes, the employees in the banking sector are exposed to various pressures causing stress. Job satisfaction has been studied both as a consequence of many individual and work environment characteristics and as an antecedent to many outcomes. Employees who have higher job satisfaction are usually less absent, less likely to leave, more productive, more likely to display organizational commitment, and more likely to be satisfied with their lives (Lease, 1998). Job satisfaction degree is in fact determined by the ratio between what we have and what we want in our life. Human have to adjust continuously with the changing environment. When a person becomes successful with his job, he feels satisfied and job satisfaction is essential for uprising production. The worker who achieves more is highly satisfied with his job. Future expectation of an employee also influences his job satisfaction level. Job satisfaction of bank employees is very important for the economic sector to function successfully.

Key Words: Job Stress, Job Satisfaction & Bank Employees

Introduction:

Competition around the world has led the corporate world to face new challenges and made them come up with their own employees a sustainable competitive advantage. This has come up with an improved attention on management of human resources, which is considered as the driving force behind the survival and success of any organization. However, uncertainty, complexity and change are the important issue for such organizations. The workplace stress is becoming a critical problem for employees, employers and the society at large. The stress induced due to Job performed by employees at workplace has been a critical organizational stressor. Job satisfaction is a unique concept (Rollison et al., 1998), but today it is seen as a very complex cluster of attitudes towards different aspects of the work. It is also a pleasurable or positive emotional state and it is related to the work that individual performs. Job satisfaction is the attitude of worker toward his occupation, rewards which he gets social, Organizational and physical characteristics of the environment in which he does his working activities. Job satisfaction can be regarded as one aspect of life satisfaction; experiences on the job influence perceptions off the job, and vice versa (Davis & Newstrom, 1989). There are some factors in job satisfaction. Some important facts for job satisfaction are pay, promotion and promotion opportunities, co-workers, supervision and the work itself. The outcomes have found to be costly to the organization. Workplace stress and Job stress is a psychological construct that people may experience every day. It is a concept which is hard to avoid. The term stress has evolved over time and has long been recognized as an inevitable aspect of life.

Stress:

Stress is a natural physical response to perception of a stimulus; It has an evolutionary purpose the need is to protect and innate, 'Flight to fight' aspects of nervous system when battling for survival. The stress is released the adrenaline that fight. So although most don't have to battle way into the office morning the response to stimuli. The stress that exist that stimulus could be something physical, such as emotional, fear of losing job or being embarrassed in the workplace. But not all sources of stress are negative stimuli some sources of stress are actually happy events. Occupational stress is a serious and enduring problem in the workplace. The last few decades have brought about dramatic changes in the nature of work in organizations. The introduction of new technology, particularly the use of computers, in the workplace, coupled with huge shift towards globalization and privatization with its inherent features of mergers, acquisition, strategic alliances and downsizing, restructured the functioning of industries. In order to compete successfully in the increasingly competitive global market, many organizations started to depend on subcontracting and outsourcing which undermine the requirements of permanent employees.

History of Stress:

The word stress is not a new one. It is as old as mankind. Since time immemorial various concepts developed by ancient Indian scholars, which relate to the phenomenon of stress. The ancient philosophical, religious texts like Ramayana and Bhagwad Gita and Various indigenous systems like Samkhya, Yoga and Ayurveda deliberate on native forms of stress. Dukha means pain; suffering, Klesha means afflictions etc. have indicated the traces of the origin of stress in India. In 1983 Rao has referred to the Samkhya and Yoga systems to point that Klesha have its origin in the root khs which means to 'torment, or cause pain. Avidya means ignorance, Asmita means egoism, Raga means attraction, Divesa means repulsion and Abhinivesa means lust for life, are the five types of Kleshas which lead to Dukha. The life is equivalent to Dukha which indicates that even pleasure and enjoyment of worldly goodness' can be a source of stress. Stress is a problem associated with the existence of the individual, accepted and consequently reflected in the Indian thought. The concept of stress, finds its roots in the field of life sciences, derived from the Latin word Stringere', which means to draw tight. In the 17th century the term 'stress' concept was used to describe affliction. In the end it started to be perceived as a physiological or medical phenomenon. During early 1900s Walter Bradford Cannon, studied the effects of stress on human being and animals in terms of the popular fight or flight' syndrome. In 2004, Cooper & Dewe, by giving the concept of 'Homeostasis', revealed that the human body has an ability to maintain its own consistency. This is done by the body naturally which in its own wisdom begins adjustments in the face of a stressor and tries to come back at a steady state

Sources of Stress:

Although there are a variety of sources of stress in people's lives, many people look for stress help in dealing with predominantly six main sources of stress.

Environmental Stress:

The stress, strain and hassle in life can be of environmental stress. This type of stress relates to those aspects of environment and surroundings that are causing stress. For example, living next to a noisy, busy street may result in exhibiting stress symptoms and stress effects.

Social Stress:

This type of stress relates to the stress involved in interacting, socializing and communicating with other human beings. It revolves around relationship with other people. Some of the social interactions and relationships can be very stressful and tension filled experiences in life. Others can be enjoyable and positive types of social stress and social interaction.

Organizational Stress:

Everyone has engaged with, belong to and is employed by the organization. This can be result in organizational stress. Experts in stress management discuss that this source of stress under the areas of environmental or social stress. Since organizations of all types play an important role in everyone lives. Most often this source of stress is associated with work stress and job stress. It often involves the demands and pressures placed upon by the organization. However; it also involves any organization

Psychological Stress:

Psychological stress involves the power of own mind in how they think, rationalize and make meaning of stress, hassles and worries. It is about how brain, psyche, mind thinks about the stress in life. It is spoken of as emotional stress or mental stress involves powerful feelings and emotions.

Significant Events Stress:

This source of stress revolves around critical incidents and significant events in of life. It is also known as significant events stress. Not all stress is bad and there are significant events that may occur in life that result in positive stress. Example, passing in high school, graduation, or winning a sporting event. However, there are significant events that involve negative stress. Often are referred to as critical incidents of life. These can be a major incident such as accident, physical or sexual assault, etc. Such events involve a very high degree of stress and anxiety. They are associated with continuing trauma after the event, referred to as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

Types of Stress:

Episodic Stress:

Episodic acute stress is the stress which affects those who suffer from acute stress and tend to suffer always seem to be in a rush, they take too much on and tend not to be able to organize themselves to deal with demands and pressures.

Chronic Stress:

Chronic Stress is a stress from repeated exposure to situations that lead to the release of stress hormones. This stress can cause wear and tear on mind and body. Many scientists thought that body stress response system is not designed to be activated constantly. This overuse may contribute to the breakdown of many bodily systems.

Stress in Banking Sector: Madan & Bajwa (2016) reported that employees working in banks face huge amount of stress specifically in private banks due to late working hours, superior subordinate relationship, manager's

attitude and financial rewards. The study by Dhankar, S. (2015) was undertaken to determine the level of stress experienced by the people and also to analyze the impact of various components of stress among the employees of 20 banks of Kurukshetra, Panipat, Sonapat and Karnal region. The results indicated that the private sector employees feel stress due to the role overload whereas the public sector employees feel more stress due to unreasonable group and political pressure

Biswakarma (2015) explored the existing Quality of Work Life in Nepal (QoWL). It also explored the relationship between the determinants of QoWL and satisfaction of QoWL among 200 employees working in different financial and non-financial institutions in Nepal. In general, the purpose of the study was to describe the level of satisfaction of QoWL and gain an understanding of difference of this phenomenon in financial and non-financial institutions in Nepal. Furthermore, the study also focused to hypothetical relationship between factors contributing to QoWL. The conceptual model developed by Laar and Easton (2012) was adopted, measured through WRQL scale 2 (2013) in 5 point Likert scale. The Cronbach's alpha for overall scale was 0.82. It is found that employees working in non-financial sector are more satisfied with QWL than employees working in financial sector in Nepal. It was found that the working conditions and employee engagement have strong relationship. It was also observed that the working conditions and employee engagement are congenial in non-financial sector in comparison with financial sector in Nepal and stress at work is lower in non-financial sector than that of financial sector in Nepal. Selva Kumar and Immanuel (2015) conducted a study in the banking sector and found that employees in both the public and private sectors face moderate levels of stress, of which they are subject to role erosion the most and resource inadequacy the least. Further, there is no significant difference in total role stress among public and private sector employees. Although they noted that private sector employees are facing slightly more stress than those in the public sector. The research conducted by Tudu and Pathak (2014) among employees of private and public sector banks of Delhi, Noida and Gurgaon, metropolitan cities of India corroborates the existence of stress among employees of both private and public sector banks. The bank employees, both private and public sector, are experiencing moderate to high level of stress. Role stagnation (RS) emerged as the most potent role stressor in both the sectors followed by Inter Role Distance (IRD) and Role Erosion (RE). Ambiguity (RA) emerged as the least potent role stressor in both banks. However, on comparing the means of both the sectors it is observed that private bank employees experienced higher overall stress. This might be due to the nature of job these professionals performance

Job Satisfaction:

Job satisfaction refers to an individuals complex attitude towards his job. It is a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of ones job as achieving as facilitating the achievement of ones job value. According to Vroom (1964) the term job' refers to workers' immediate work task and work role in a particular work organization.

Job satisfaction can simply be defined as how people feel about their jobs. It is the attitude that an individual carries towards a job, also known as the general disposition towards a job. It can be defined as a pleasurable (or unpleasurable) emotional state because of the appraisal of ones job, an affective reaction to ones job, and an attitude a person carries towards his job. These definitions show that job satisfaction takes into account feelings, beliefs and behaviours. Job satisfaction can be influenced by a number of factors.

Dimensions of Job Satisfaction:

There are three important dimensions to job satisfaction.

- ✓ Job satisfaction refers to ones feeling towards ones job. It can only be inferred but not seen.
- ✓ Job satisfaction is often determined by how well outcomes meet or exceed expectations. Satisfaction in one's job means increased commitment in the fulfillment of formal requirements. There is greater willingness to invest personal energy and time in job performance.
- ✓ The terms job satisfaction and job attitudes are typically used interchangeably. Both refers to effective orientation on the part of individuals towards their work roles which they are presently occupying. Positive attitudes towards the job are conceptually equivalent to job satisfaction and negative attitudes towards the job indicate job dissatisfaction

Sources of Job Satisfaction:

Several job elements contribute to job satisfaction. The most important amongst them are wage structure, nature of work, promotion chances, policies of the organisms, work group and working conditions

Wages:

Wages play a significant role in influencing job satisfaction. This is because of two reasons. First, money is an important instrument in fulfilling ones needs; and too, employees often see pay as a reflection of management is concern for them.

Nature of Work:

Most employees crave for intellectual challenges on jobs. They tend to prefer being given opportunities to use their skills and attitudes and being offered a variety of tasks, freedom, and feedback on how well they are doing. These characteristics make jobs mentally challenging. Jobs that have too little challenge create boredom.

But too much challenge creates frustration and a feeling of failure. Under conditions of moderate challenge, employees experience pleasure and satisfaction.

Promotions:

Promotional opportunities affect job satisfaction considerably. The desire for promotion is generally strong among employees as it involves change in job content, pay, responsibility, independence, status and the like. An average employee in a typical government organization can hope to get two or three promotion in his entire service, though chances for promotion are better in the private sector. It is no surprise as the ultimate achievement in his career is realised, he feels extremely satisfied.

Supervision:

There is a positive relationship between the quality of supervision and job satisfaction. Supervisors who establish a supportive personal relationship with subordinates and take a personal concern in them contribute to their employees' satisfaction.

Work Group:

The work group plays a significant role in providing satisfaction to individual employees. It does so, primarily by providing group members, with opportunities for interaction, with each other. It is well known that, for many employees work fills the need for social interaction.

Working Conditions:

Working conditions that are compatible with an employee's physical comfort and that facilitate doing a good job contribute to job satisfaction. Temperature, humidity ventilation, lighting and noise, hours of work, cleanliness of the work place, and adequate tools and equipment are the features which affect job satisfaction

Organizational Policies and Procedures:

Organizational policies include the basis for effecting promotions (seniority versus merit), transfer of people, foreign assignments, lay off and retrenchment appraisal and reward systems, motivational methods, skill based versus job based, pay and the like

Consequences of Job Satisfaction:

High job satisfaction may lead to improved productivity, increased turnover, improved attendance, reduced accidents, less job stress and lower unionization

Productivity:

The relationship between satisfaction and productivity is not definitely established. The consensus, however, is that in the long run job satisfaction leads to increased productivity. But, four decades of research into this issue, unfortunately, does not lend support to this belief.

First, the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance is weak. Second, there is more evidence to suggest that job performance leads to job satisfaction and not the other way round. An employee who performs well in his job gets both intrinsic and extrinsic rewards which will lead to high satisfaction. A poor performer will feel worse about his incompetence and will receive fewer rewards. He will be less satisfied with his work experiences.

Third, there are some conditions under which high productivity more clearly leads to high job satisfaction. One condition is that the employees perceive that intrinsic and extrinsic rewards are contingent upon their productivity. The second condition is that the extrinsic rewards (pay, for example) may be distributed equitably. Inequitable distribution fails to convince the employees close correlation between hard work and rewards. However, the adage "a happy worker is a productive worker" is not always wrong. True, there may not be a relationship between job satisfaction and productivity; performance may be affected indirectly by absenteeism or turnover which is related (negatively) to satisfaction

Stress and Job Satisfaction among Bank Employees:

Stress is the body's response to any job related factor that threatens to disturb the persons equilibrium. In the process of experiencing stress, the employees' inner state changes. Prolonged stress can cause serious ailments such as heart disease, ulcer, blurred vision, lower back pain, dermatitis, and muscle aches to the employees. Chronic job - dissatisfaction is a powerful source of job stress. The employee may see no satisfactory short term solution to escaping this type of stress. An employee trapped in a dissatisfying job may withdraw by such means as high absenteeism and tardiness, or the employee may quit. Employees under prolonged stress stemming from job dissatisfaction often consume too much alcohol, tobacco and drugs. These employees are costly to the management in terms of time lost due to frequent absences and increased payments towards medical reimbursements.

Quality employees lose their enthusiasm for their work and eventually withdraw from the company. More satisfied workers are less likely to leave their employer (Clark, 2001), have lower rates of absenteeism (Clegg, 1983) and have higher productivity (Mangione and Quinn, 1975). Some internal factors of job stress may be poor working condition, shift work, long working time travel, risk, salary, person-job mismatch, new technology, and work over under load. A study showed that job stress is higher for the employees dissatisfied with their jobs than the satisfied ones (Rahman and Sorcar, 1990). It is also showed in another study that a positive correlation is found between job satisfaction and job performance which in agreement with the popular

'human relations' view that a satisfied worker is a more productive worker. (Haque,1992). Both satisfaction with pay and job security are the most important job satisfaction categories for determining future quits, while satisfaction with promotion opportunities is not a significant factor (Clark, 2001). Job stress also depends on gender and personality. In a study, where results show that as compared to male workers greater number of female workers consider their job stressful. The result also revealed that the female workers reported comparatively more health complaints than the male workers (Wadud, 1996).

Job satisfaction is defined as all the feelings that an individual has about his/her job (Sowmya and Panchanatham, 2011). Job satisfaction is associated with increased output, efficiency of the organization, loyalty with the organization, and reduced absenteeism and earnings (Ellickson & Logsdon, 2001; Wright & Davis, 2003), however, if employees are not satisfied with the job then it may cause turnover intentions, increasing costs, decreasing profits and ultimately customer unhappiness with the organization (Zeffane et al., 2008). Over years, an attempt has been made to categorize and find out the factors that affect job satisfaction and found wages as the main factor for job satisfaction, but other factors such as the promotion, recognition of work, and employees loyalty are also considered important (as cited in Salem et al., 2013). Nevertheless, Calisir et al., (2010) asserts that salaries and incentives are the most important determinant of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is an attitude or emotional response to work task as well as to the physical and social conditions of the work place and Job Stress is one of the determinants which may affect the job satisfaction of an employee (Jagtap & Yadav, 2014). Stress causes a reduction in the effectiveness of the organisation, high de ertion rates, low morale, and low job satisfaction (Jimmieseon, Terry & Callan, 2004). In occupational stress model, it was found that job stress and job satisfaction are distinct, but highly interrelated variables. According to Seaward's (2005) findings, the ability of employees to properly control and manage their job stress will lead to have higher job satisfaction. Bank employees cannot afford the time to relax and they are faced with work variety, discrimination, favoritism, delegation, and conflicting tasks.

Conclusion:

In the present economic environment of job insecurity, flatter organizations, and intense work pressures, there are quite a few managers who feel trapped where they are and such a feeling of being in a rut can turn into a persistent source of stress. If we feel frustrated in that job, we ought to do something about it. When we see successful People, we tend to assume that their careers have been smooth upward paths. It is not so, people who are seen to move up the management ladder step by step have no secret ticket or password. They simply work hard, watch for opportunities, await their turn, prepare and equip themselves for the bigger roles, and maintain a positive outlook on life. Secondly, it is not always necessary to switch jobs, to make our professional life more interesting and rewarding. Let us not presume that we have no power or means to improve the profile or life-style of the job, which we are now doing. Where there is a will, there is a way. If we have a good idea, we must preserve with it refuse to accept a negative response, and leave no stone unturned until we get it implemented. The sense of fulfillment and achievement which ensue, will elicit enduring satisfaction. What is more, a track record of such determination and indefatigable zeal cannot be ignored for too long, and the rewards will follow sooner or later. When we lack the ability and skill to deal with any situation, stress is bound to occur. Stress management involves three main types of intervention. They are stress prevention, employee training, and employee counseling programme. We ought to observe that there is a cyclical nature in the sequence of these interventions. Employee counseling programme is a voluntary and confidential service, which provides help to employees and their immediate families in dealing with their personal, or work - related issues. Banks should take steps to improve training and opportunities for career advancement. To increase the level of satisfaction of the bank employees it is necessary to improve policy for career development. Job satisfaction and dissatisfaction of Bank employees should be evaluated periodically for evolving dynamic and pragmatic policies for organization's growth and development. Banks should pay attention to the extent of direction employees receive from their boss since they are exhibiting lower level of satisfaction in this regard.

References:

1. Biswakarma, G. (2015). Quality of Work life in Nepal: A comparative study of financial and nonfinancial Institutions. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences*, 3(8), 19-26
2. Clark, A. E. (2001). "What really matters in a job? Hedonic measurement using quit data." *Labour Economics*, Vol. 8, 223-242.
3. Clegg, C. W. (1983). "Psychology of employee lateness, absence, and turnover: a methodological critique and an empirical study." *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 68 (1), 88-101.
4. Dhankar, S. (2015). Occupational stress in banking sector. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(8), 132-135
5. Haque, A. B. M. Z. Quality of Working Life and Job Satisfaction of Industrial Workers In Relation to Size of The Organization *Bangladesh Psychological Studies*, 1992. Vol. 2, No. 1, 43-55.
6. Kumar SG, Unnikrishnan B, Nagaraj K. Self-reported chronic diseases and occupational health risks among bank employees of southern Karnataka City, India. *Indian J Community Med*. 2013;38:61-2

7. Lima CT, Farrell M, Prince M. Job strain, hazardous drinking, and alcohol-related disorders among Brazilian bank workers. *J Stud Alcohol Drugs*. 2013;74:212–22
8. Mangione, T.W. and Quinn, R.W. (1975), “Job satisfaction, counterproductive behavior and drug use at work.” *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 60, 114-116
9. Michailidis M, Georgiou Y. Employee occupational stress in banking. *Work*. 2005; 24:123–37.
10. Preshita Neha Tudu and Pramod Pathak (2014). A Comparative Study of Occupational Stress among Public and Private Sector Bank Employees of India: A Research Review. *I J A B E R*, 12 (3), 831- 841
11. Rahman, A. and Sorcar, N. R. Occupational Stress, Marital Status and Job Satisfaction of Working Women. *The Dhaka University Studies, part-C*, 1990. Vol. 11 (1) : 55-61
12. Temcharoen P, Vorapongsathorn T, Pradipasen M, Sritara P. A longitudinal causal relationship among cardiovascular risk factors in the employees of the government savings bank. *J Med Assoc Thai*. 2002; 85:863–74.
13. Wadud, Nasreen, Job Stress of Male and Female Industrial Workers in Bangladesh *Journal of Psychology*. 1996-96. Vol. 15, pp. 65-100.
14. Xavier Selvakumar and Lawrence Immanuel (2015). Employees Stress Management in Public and Private Sector Banks in Nagapattinam District An Analysis. *Asia Pacific Journal of Research*, 1(26), 93-102